

MedVetKlebs	WP1: <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> from Chicken Meat	Rev. 3 13 th February 2019
-------------	---	--

Optimisation of Methods for Isolation of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from Chicken Meat

Metadata of the samples

Prior to testing chicken meat samples record the following sample details:

- Date
- Manufacturer
- Country of origin
- Batch number
- Meat cuts: chicken leg or chicken fillet
- Farming system: Free range/not free range.

Procedure

Preparation of the test samples and initial suspension

1. Cut sample into small slivers to a final weight of 25g.
2. Dilute the 25g portion in 225ml of **BPW broth** (1:10 dilution) (Pre-warm the BPW at room temperature before use)
3. Mix the sample using a stomacher for 30 seconds or pulse using a blender.
4. Incubate the suspension at **37 °C ± 1°C** for 24 h ± 1 h.
5. Following 24h incubation, using a **10µl loop**, streak for single colonies onto the surface of a small petri dish (90 mm) of SCAI medium and incubate at **44°C ± 1°C for 48 h ± 1 h**.

Purification and Identification of suspect *K. pneumoniae*

Typical *Klebsiella* spp. colonies are yellow on SCAI medium.

6. Select suspect *Klebsiella pneumoniae* colonies¹ (if there are several morphotypes, take one or two of each) from each plate for subculture and bacterial identification. **Sweep the remaining plate content and freeze it at -80°C (for mixed colonies sequencing)** using CryoBank tubes or equivalent (e.g. *in house* BHI + 15% glycerol medium).
7. Streak the selected colonies¹ onto the surface of a non-selective agar (e.g. LB or TSA) medium in a manner which will allow isolated colonies to develop. Incubate plates at 37 °C ± 1°C for 24 h ± 1 h.
8. Determine **species ID** in all purified suspect *K. pneumoniae* colonies using MALDI-TOF MS and/or qPCR ID phylogroups.

MedVetKlebs	WP1: <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> from Chicken Meat	Rev. 3 13 th February 2019
-------------	---	--

9. Freeze only isolates confirmed as *Klebsiella pneumoniae* complex at -80°C using CryoBank tubes or equivalent (e.g. BHI + 15% glycerol medium). Store only one isolate *per* morphotype.

¹NOTE: If colonies are numerous and close to each other, re-isolate the colony on another SCAI agar plate to control for purity. Incubate for up to 48h.

Expression of results

- Document all results obtained and take images of all SCAI plates following incubation.

DRAFT

MedVetKlebs	WP1: <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> from Chicken Meat	Rev. 3 13 th February 2019
-------------	---	--

Annex A: Workflow diagram and procedure for the isolation of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from chicken meat samples

- Purify and ID colonies; select 1 colony *per* morphotype confirmed to be either *K. pneumoniae*, *K. variicola* or *K. quasipneumoniae* (*i.e.*, Kp complex) and freeze it.
- Sweep all the plate content and freeze it at -80°C (for mixed colonies sequencing)